

The influence of neural field microstructure on the process of the spread of traveling waves

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We have the following the two-dimensional homogenized Amari neural field equation

$$\partial_t u(t, \mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) = -u(t, \mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) + \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} \int_Y \omega(|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}'|, \mathbf{y} - \mathbf{y}') f(u(t, \mathbf{x}', \mathbf{y}')) d\mathbf{y}' d\mathbf{x}', \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}' \in \mathbb{R}^2$ and $\mathbf{y} \in Y = [0, 1]^2$. The weight distribution function $\omega(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y})$ is taken to be positive function in $\mathbf{L}^1(\mathbb{R}_+^2, Y)$ and periodically modulated for the local scale \mathbf{y} . We denote by $\langle \omega \rangle$ to the average connectivity function ω over the unit cell, i.e.,

$$\langle \omega \rangle(\mathbf{x}) = \int_Y \omega(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) d\mathbf{y} \quad \forall \mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^2.$$

For the activation function $f : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ we assume that $0 \leq f \leq 1$. The firing-rate function $f(u)$ for Amari model is chosen to be the Heaviside step function. Thus, we have

$$\partial_t u(t, \mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) = -u(t, \mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) + \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} \int_Y \omega(|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}'|, \mathbf{y} - \mathbf{y}') H(u(t, \mathbf{x}', \mathbf{y}')) d\mathbf{y}' d\mathbf{x}'. \quad (2)$$

For the question of stability of the ring solutions, we are going to proceed a way analogous to Elena Malyutina et al. [2] and [3]. Let consider the time independent perturbation solution by writing $u(t, \mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) = U(\mathbf{x}) + v(t, \mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y})$ where $U(\mathbf{x})$ is a radially symmetric smooth bounded function for all $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}$ (i.e., $U(\mathbf{x}) = U(r)$ for $\mathbf{x} = (r, \theta)$ with $r \in \mathbb{R}_+$ and $\theta \in [0, 2\pi)$) denotes to a bump stationary solution of the equation (2) that satisfies the following conditions:

- $U(\pm\infty) = 0$,
- there are unique points denoted by $b > a > 0$ such that $U(a) = U(b) = h$, $h \in \mathbb{R}$, where we have assumed

$$\begin{aligned} U(r) &> h \text{ when } r \in (-b, -a) \cup (a, b) \\ U(r) &< h \text{ when } r \in (-\infty, -b) \cup (-a, a) \cup (b, \infty), \end{aligned}$$

and $v(t, \mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y})$ represents a small perturbation of $U(\mathbf{x})$. By Taylor expanding of the equation (2) about $U(\mathbf{x})$ to the first order in $v(t, \mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y})$ leads to the following linearized equation

$$\partial_t v(t, \mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) = -v(t, \mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) + \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} \int_Y \omega(|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}'|, \mathbf{y} - \mathbf{y}') H'(U(r') - h) v(t, \mathbf{x}', \mathbf{y}') d\mathbf{y}' d\mathbf{x}'. \quad (3)$$

By separating the spacial variables from the time variable by writing $v(t, \mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) = \varphi(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) e^{\lambda t}$, $\lambda \in \mathbb{C}$ we get

$$(1 + \lambda)\varphi(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) = \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} \int_Y \omega(|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}'|, \mathbf{y} - \mathbf{y}') H'(U(r') - h) \varphi(\mathbf{x}', \mathbf{y}') d\mathbf{y}' d\mathbf{x}'. \quad (4)$$

Here λ plays the role of growth rate ($\text{Re}\lambda > 0$) or decay rate ($\text{Re}\lambda < 0$) of the perturbation $v(t, \mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y})$ imposed on the stationary pulse state $U(\mathbf{x})$. Then, by introducing polar coordinates $\mathbf{x} = (r, \theta)$ and $\mathbf{x}' = (r', \theta')$ with $r, r' \in \mathbb{R}_+$ and $\theta, \theta' \in [0, 2\pi)$, and using the result

$$\begin{aligned} H'(U(r)) &= \delta(U(r)) = \frac{\delta(r-a)}{|U'(a)|} + \frac{\delta(r-b)}{|U'(b)|}, \\ U'(a) &= \langle \omega \rangle(2a) - \langle \omega \rangle(0) \\ U'(b) &= \langle \omega \rangle(2b) - \langle \omega \rangle(0) \end{aligned}$$

where δ here is the Dirac delta function. Therefor, we obtain the following

$$\begin{aligned} &\int_{\mathbb{R}^2} \omega(|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}'|, \mathbf{y} - \mathbf{y}') H'(U(r')) \varphi(\mathbf{x}', \mathbf{y}') d\mathbf{x}' \\ &= \frac{a}{|U'(a)|} \int_0^{2\pi} \omega\left(\sqrt{r^2 + a^2 - 2ra \cos(\theta - \theta'_a)}, \mathbf{y} - \mathbf{y}'\right) \varphi(a, \theta'_a, \mathbf{y}') d\theta' \\ &+ \frac{b}{|U'(b)|} \int_0^{2\pi} \omega\left(\sqrt{r^2 + b^2 - 2rb \cos(\theta - \theta'_b)}, \mathbf{y} - \mathbf{y}'\right) \varphi(b, \theta'_b, \mathbf{y}') d\theta'. \end{aligned}$$

Hence, the equation (4) becomes

$$\begin{aligned} (1 + \lambda)\varphi(r, \theta, \mathbf{y}) &= \frac{a}{|U'(a)|} \int_0^{2\pi} \int_Y \omega\left(\sqrt{r^2 + a^2 - 2ra \cos(\theta - \theta'_a)}, \mathbf{y} - \mathbf{y}'\right) \varphi(a, \theta'_a, \mathbf{y}') d\mathbf{y}' d\theta' \\ &+ \frac{b}{|U'(b)|} \int_0^{2\pi} \int_Y \omega\left(\sqrt{r^2 + b^2 - 2rb \cos(\theta - \theta'_b)}, \mathbf{y} - \mathbf{y}'\right) \varphi(b, \theta'_b, \mathbf{y}') d\mathbf{y}' d\theta'. \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

We look for solutions of the form $\varphi(r, \theta, \mathbf{y}) = \varphi_l(r, \mathbf{y})e^{il\theta}$, where $l \in \mathbb{Z}$. Hence, radial perturbations away from the borders of the ring are completely determined by the perturbation at the ring edges (where $r = a$ and $r = b$). Taking $r = a$ then $r = b$ in (5) we get the following system of two equations

$$\begin{aligned} (1 + \lambda)\varphi_l(a, \mathbf{y}) &= \frac{a}{|U'(a)|} \int_0^{2\pi} \int_Y \omega\left(\sqrt{2a^2 - 2a^2 \cos(\phi)}, \mathbf{y} - \mathbf{y}'\right) \varphi_l(a, \mathbf{y}') \cos(l\phi) d\mathbf{y}' d\phi \\ &+ \frac{b}{|U'(b)|} \int_0^{2\pi} \int_Y \omega\left(\sqrt{a^2 + b^2 - 2ba \cos(\phi)}, \mathbf{y} - \mathbf{y}'\right) \varphi_l(b, \mathbf{y}') \cos(l\phi) d\mathbf{y}' d\phi; \end{aligned} \quad (6a)$$

$$\begin{aligned} (1 + \lambda)\varphi_l(b, \mathbf{y}) &= \frac{a}{|U'(a)|} \int_0^{2\pi} \int_Y \omega\left(\sqrt{b^2 + a^2 - 2ba \cos(\phi)}, \mathbf{y} - \mathbf{y}'\right) \varphi_l(a, \mathbf{y}') \cos(l\phi) d\mathbf{y}' d\phi \\ &+ \frac{b}{|U'(b)|} \int_0^{2\pi} \int_Y \omega\left(\sqrt{2b^2 - 2b^2 \cos(\phi)}, \mathbf{y} - \mathbf{y}'\right) \varphi_l(b, \mathbf{y}') \cos(l\phi) d\mathbf{y}' d\phi, \end{aligned} \quad (6b)$$

where a and b are the simultaneous solutions of the equation $u(a, \mathbf{y}) = u(b, \mathbf{y}) = h$ with $a < b$. The previous system of equations can be written under the following format as an eigenvalue problem

$$\mu\Phi = \mathcal{H}\Phi \quad (7)$$

where the multiplication operator \mathcal{H} is defined as

$$[\mathcal{H}\Phi](\mathbf{y}) = \mathcal{W}(\mathbf{y}) ** \Phi(\mathbf{y})$$

where $(**)$ denotes to the two-dimensional convolution operator with respect to \mathbf{y} ,

$$\mathcal{W}_l(\mathbf{y}) = \begin{pmatrix} a|U'(b)| \int_0^{2\pi} \omega\left(\sqrt{2a^2 - 2a^2 \cos(\phi)}, \mathbf{y}\right) \cos(l\phi) d\phi & b|U'(a)| \int_0^{2\pi} \omega\left(\sqrt{a^2 + b^2 - 2ba \cos(\phi)}, \mathbf{y}\right) \cos(l\phi) d\phi \\ a|U'(b)| \int_0^{2\pi} \omega\left(\sqrt{b^2 + a^2 - 2ba \cos(\phi)}, \mathbf{y}\right) \cos(l\phi) d\phi & b|U'(a)| \int_0^{2\pi} \omega\left(\sqrt{2b^2 - 2b^2 \cos(\phi)}, \mathbf{y}\right) \cos(l\phi) d\phi \end{pmatrix},$$

$$\Phi_l(\mathbf{y}) = \begin{pmatrix} \varphi_l(a, \mathbf{y}) \\ \varphi_l(b, \mathbf{y}) \end{pmatrix}$$

and $\mu = (\lambda + 1)|U'(a)||U'(b)|$.

The main issue now consists of defining the spectrum of the operator \mathcal{H} . We first note that \mathcal{H} is a compact linear but not self-adjoint operator. It has a spectral theory that can be understood in terms of a discrete spectrum of eigenvalues that tend to 0.

Using the Fourier decomposition method we next determine the eigenvalues of the operator \mathcal{H} and this will be analogous to Owen et al. [1]. This method can be considered as constructing an Evans function for each Fourier mode.

Let's now introduce Fourier series expansion with respect the variable \mathbf{y} . For $\mathbf{y} = (y_1, y_2) \in Y$ the Fourier expansion is written as

$$\Phi_l(\mathbf{y}) = \Phi_l(y_1, y_2) = \sum_{m=-\infty}^{\infty} \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} \hat{\Phi}_{lmn} e^{2i\pi m y_1} e^{2i\pi n y_2}, \quad \text{for all } m, n \in \mathbb{Z},$$

where

$$\hat{\Phi}_{lmn} = \int_Y \Phi_l(y_1, y_2) e^{-2i\pi m y_1} e^{-2i\pi n y_2} dy_1 dy_2.$$

Using the Fourier series representation and the convolution theorem in the equation (7) we get the following eigenvalue problem

$$\mu \hat{\Phi}_{lmn} = \hat{\mathcal{W}}_{lmn} \hat{\Phi}_{lmn}, \quad \forall l, m, n \in \mathbb{Z}. \quad (8)$$

It follows that the infinite sequence of Evans functions

$$\mathcal{E}_{lmn}(\lambda) := \det(\mu \mathbf{I} - \hat{\mathcal{W}}_{lmn}), \quad \forall l, m, n \in \mathbb{Z}$$

corresponding to the model in the Fourier expansion for the perturbations. Here, \mathbf{I} denotes the 2×2 identity matrix. The zeros of the Evans function correspond to eigenvalues of the linearized problem (7) that determine the location of the point spectrum and can be used to locate solution stability (the essential spectrum being restricted to the left-hand complex plan).

Hence, the eigenvalues of $\hat{\mathcal{W}}_{lmn}$ are given by

$$\mu_{lmn}^{\pm} = \frac{\text{tr}(\hat{\mathcal{W}}_{lmn}) \pm \sqrt{(\text{tr}(\hat{\mathcal{W}}_{lmn}))^2 - 4 \det(\hat{\mathcal{W}}_{lmn})}}{2}.$$

Moreover, the expressions of the growth/decay rates are

$$\lambda_{lmn}^{\pm} = \frac{\mu_{lmn}^{\pm}}{|U'(a)||U'(b)|} - 1.$$

Since by assumption the component functions of \mathcal{W} are real-valued continuous and even functions of the variable \mathbf{y} , we find that the component functions of $\hat{\mathcal{W}}_{lmn}$ are real-valued and even, and the eigenvalues μ_{lmn}^{\pm} are real and satisfy $\mu_{lmn}^{\pm} = \mu_{l-m-n}^{\pm}$. Then, in this case we need only to consider the eigenvalues for $m, n = 0, 1, 2, \dots$

Now, let study the stability of the ring solution in function of the heterogeneity parameter γ . Let assume that the connectivity kernel function ω_γ depends to a parameter γ , which measures the degree of heterogeneity. Notice that, the case $\gamma = 0$ corresponds to the two-dimensional ring solution in the translationally invariant case. We assume that the connectivity function ω is periodically modulated in the local variable y .

Let denote by $\omega^\gamma \equiv \omega(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}; \gamma)$ to the connectivity function of the parameter γ and by ω^0 to the connectivity function when $\gamma = 0$. We have

$$\mathcal{W}_l^\gamma(\mathbf{y}) = \begin{pmatrix} a|U'(b)| \int_0^{2\pi} \omega(\sqrt{2a^2 - 2a^2 \cos(\phi)}, \mathbf{y}; \gamma) \cos(l\phi) d\phi & b|U'(a)| \int_0^{2\pi} \omega(\sqrt{a^2 + b^2 - 2ba \cos(\phi)}, \mathbf{y}; \gamma) \cos(l\phi) d\phi \\ a|U'(b)| \int_0^{2\pi} \omega(\sqrt{b^2 + a^2 - 2ba \cos(\phi)}, \mathbf{y}; \gamma) \cos(l\phi) d\phi & b|U'(a)| \int_0^{2\pi} \omega(\sqrt{2b^2 - 2b^2 \cos(\phi)}, \mathbf{y}; \gamma) \cos(l\phi) d\phi \end{pmatrix}.$$

We find, for any fixed \mathbf{x} , that ω^γ converges to $\omega^0(\mathbf{x})$ uniformly as γ tends to 0 and thus $\mathcal{W}_l^\gamma(\mathbf{y})$ converges to \mathcal{W}_l^0 uniformly as $\gamma \rightarrow 0$ with

$$\mathcal{W}_l^0 = \begin{pmatrix} a|U'(b)| \int_0^{2\pi} \omega(\sqrt{2a^2 - 2a^2 \cos(\phi)}) \cos(l\phi) d\phi & b|U'(a)| \int_0^{2\pi} \omega(\sqrt{a^2 + b^2 - 2ba \cos(\phi)}) \cos(l\phi) d\phi \\ a|U'(b)| \int_0^{2\pi} \omega(\sqrt{b^2 + a^2 - 2ba \cos(\phi)}) \cos(l\phi) d\phi & b|U'(a)| \int_0^{2\pi} \omega(\sqrt{2b^2 - 2b^2 \cos(\phi)}) \cos(l\phi) d\phi \end{pmatrix}.$$

Therefor, the eigenvalues of $\mu_l^{\pm, \gamma}$ and the growth/decay rates $\lambda_l^{\pm, \gamma}$ given by respectively

$$\mu_l^{\pm, \gamma} = \frac{\text{tr}(\widehat{\mathcal{W}}_l^\gamma) \pm \sqrt{(\text{tr}(\widehat{\mathcal{W}}_l^\gamma))^2 - 4 \det(\widehat{\mathcal{W}}_l^\gamma)}}{2}, \quad \lambda_l^{\pm, \gamma} = \frac{\mu_l^{\pm, \gamma}}{|U'(a)||U'(b)|} - 1$$

converge uniformly as $\gamma \rightarrow 0$ to $\mu_l^{\pm, 0}$ and $\lambda_l^{\pm, 0}$, respectively.

Now, we consider the Fourier representation series $\widehat{\omega}_{lmn}^\gamma$ of the connectivity function $\omega_l^\gamma(\mathbf{y})$ with respect of $\mathbf{y} = (y_1, y_2)$. We have, using Riemann-Lebesgue's lemma, that

$$\sup_{l, m, n \in \mathbb{N} \cup \{0\}} |\widehat{\omega}_{lmn}^\gamma - \widehat{\omega}_{lmn}^0| \leq \|\omega^\gamma - \omega^0\|_\infty \rightarrow 0 \text{ as } \gamma \rightarrow 0,$$

which follows that, $\widehat{\omega}_{lmn}^\gamma$ converge to $\widehat{\omega}_{lmn}^0$ uniformly as γ tends to 0. We are permitted now to interchange limit and integration, so that

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{\gamma \rightarrow 0} \widehat{\omega}_{lmn}^\gamma &= \lim_{\gamma \rightarrow 0} \int_Y \widehat{\omega}_l^\gamma(y_1, y_2) e^{-2i\pi m y_1} e^{-2i\pi n y_2} d\mathbf{y} \\ &= \int_Y \lim_{\gamma \rightarrow 0} \widehat{\omega}_l^\gamma(y_1, y_2) e^{-2i\pi m y_1} e^{-2i\pi n y_2} d\mathbf{y} \\ &= \widehat{\omega}_l^0 \int_Y e^{-2i\pi m y_1} e^{-2i\pi n y_2} d\mathbf{y}. \end{aligned}$$

We readily find that:

For $m = n = 0$, it follows that

$$\int_Y e^{-2i\pi m y_1} e^{-2i\pi n y_2} d\mathbf{y} = 1,$$

and thus, $\lim_{\gamma \rightarrow 0} \widehat{\omega}_{lmn}^\gamma = \widehat{\omega}_l^0$. In this case, the eigenvalues $\mu_{lmn}^{\pm, \gamma}$ and the growth/decay rates $\lambda_{lmn}^{\pm, \gamma}$ converge respectively to

$$\mu_l^\pm = \frac{\text{tr}(\widehat{\mathcal{W}}_l) \pm \sqrt{(\text{tr}(\widehat{\mathcal{W}}_l))^2 - 4 \det(\widehat{\mathcal{W}}_l)}}{2}, \quad \lambda_l^\pm = \frac{\mu_l^\pm}{|U'(a)||U'(b)|} - 1$$

uniformly as $\gamma \rightarrow 0$. The result is identified with the result obtained by Owen et al. [1] for the translationally invariant Wilson-Cowan model. In analogous way, we can prove for $m = n = 0$ that $\hat{\omega}_{l0}^\gamma$ converge to $\hat{\omega}_{l0}^0$ uniformly as γ tends to 0 and $\lim_{\gamma \rightarrow 0} \hat{\omega}_{l0}^\gamma = \hat{\omega}_l^0$ which gives the same result μ_l^\pm and λ_l^\pm .

For $m, n \in \mathbb{N}$, we have the limit

$$\lim_{\gamma \rightarrow 0} \hat{\omega}_{lmn}^\gamma = \hat{\omega}_l^0 \int_Y e^{-2i\pi m y_1} e^{-2i\pi n y_2} d\mathbf{y}$$

uniformly as $\gamma \rightarrow 0$. We have that

$$\lim_{l \rightarrow \infty} \hat{\omega}_l^0 \int_Y e^{-2i\pi m y_1} e^{-2i\pi n y_2} d\mathbf{y} = 0;$$

or

$$\lim_{m, n \rightarrow \infty} \hat{\omega}_l^0 \int_Y e^{-2i\pi m y_1} e^{-2i\pi n y_2} d\mathbf{y} = 0.$$

Then, the eigenvalues μ_{lmn}^\pm converge to 0 and the growth/decay λ_{lmn}^\pm converge to -1 as l or m or n tend to ∞ .

Figure 1: The growth/decay rates λ^\pm for the translationally invariant case with $l = 0$.

References

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